

Challenging Experiences of Senior High School Working Students in Selected Public Schools in Polangui North District

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Abstract:- This study appraised the Challenging experiences of Senior High School working students. This qualitative phenomenological study determined the academic performance of the respondents and described the challenging experiences encountered by the senior high school working students. The researcher used the qualitative design in this study specifically using case study. In this study, focus group discussion was used as a qualitative approach to gain an in depth understanding of social issues. By using thematic content analysis method, outcomes have been processed and revealed that working students can gain a lot of various benefits from working while studying. However, most students feel that having these jobs can distract them from their studies. The academic performance of the respondents depends on how the working students handle their time-management. This study concludes that the challenging experiences encountered by the respondents along time-management, are: lack time for working on activity that they are always late in submitting their prepared activity. In terms of their, academic performance, they are having passing grades but low.

Keywords:- Challenging Experiences, Working Students, Phenomenological Study, Polangui North District, Polangui, Albay.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a weapon to improve one's life. It is probably the most important tool to change one's life. Education for a child begins at home. It is a lifelong process that ends with death. Education certainly determines the quality of an individual's life. Education improves one's knowledge, skills and develops the personality and attitude. Most noteworthy, Education affects the chances of employment for people. A highly educated individual is probably very likely to get a good job. Education is extremely important for employment. It certainly is a great opportunity to make a decent living. This is due to the skills of a high paying job that Education provides. Uneducated people are probably at a huge disadvantage when it comes to jobs. It seems like many poor people improve their lives with the help of Education. Education is really a weapon in order to have a better life this is why there are students choose to become a working student just to sustain and finish their studies. Working and studying at the same time is tough for

working students because the time between studies and work should be balanced. Students holds two responsibilities in giving a lot of effort in the job while maintaining good academic performance in the class.

Working double shifts are excruciating, but sometimes we need those additional hours for our subsequent pay check. Students find it most difficult to set their priorities. May it be studying or work; they can never judge what is more important. Working late hours or double shifts affect studies in a great way and sometimes can lead to big-time failure because of this student not completing their academic papers like essays or assignments and they always want someone who can write essay or need services from experts. It is, therefore, necessary for a working student to seek professional assistance in regard to the priorities. Prioritizing everything helps in organizing and managing every task, accordingly. Just a single step can definitely bring a drastic change in life.

It is true to conclude that hard work really pays off but one should understand the direction in which they are utilizing their skills. A student can never appreciate the value of independence until he takes the decision of pursuing a tough lifestyle. Working while learning can be a good example of a blessing in disguise.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ *Delimitation of the Study:*

This study focused on the Challenging Experiences of Senior High School Working Students in North District Polangui Selected Public Senior High School. The target schools to be conducted of the survey are the following: Ponso National High School, Polangui General Comprehensive High School, Itaran National High School, these schools are covered by North District Polangui and the schools to be conducted of the study. The researcher choose these three schools due to it is near to her residence. This study focus on the challenging experiences of the Senior High School Working Students by conducting an in-depth interview, survey and focused-group discussion so it does not require to use quantitative design study due to the data needed by the researcher will not rely on numerical or measurable data and this will only analyze and interpret the answers of the participants regarding with their views and challenging experiences on playing the role together as

worker and student. The researcher will collect the total enumeration of the working students from Grade 11 and Grade 12 students from the three schools. The respondent in this study are the students enrolled in this school year 2022-2023. The time limitation of the study is 2022-2023 only.

➤ *Research Design:*

The research design applied in this study is qualitative research, specifically using case study. In this study, Focus group discussion was used as a qualitative approach to gain an in depth understanding of social issues. The method aims to obtain data from a purposely selected group of individuals rather than from representative sample of a broader population and which is not statistically measurable because it would only be used to generate ideas, develop hypothesis, explore motivation, and test reactions. According to Hermawan et al. (2021). An Overview of Learning Motivation Among Working Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic. This research uses criterion sampling technique in selecting four participants. The research was conducted from September 2020 to December 2020, followed by the in-depth interviews with the four participants. The results of the study indicate that all participants still have motivation to learn both intrinsically and extrinsically even though they have to strictly manage their time between working and studying, to earn a living and to master new knowledge applicable before getting a job, but one of the participants had a poor grade at college because of working. In the present study, the researcher used focus group discussion and in-depth interview as a qualitative approach to gain an in depth understanding of social issues and obtain data from a purposely selected group of individuals. Qualitative research is a research design that puts premium or high value on people's thinking or point of view conditioned by their traits (Baraceros, 2016). Phenomenology is a type of qualitative research, which is concerned, with the study of experience from the perception of the individual (Hale & Napier, 2013). The method of research used in the study is an in-depth interview because the researcher is aiming to determine the challenging experiences of the working students. An in-depth interview is a type of qualitative research technique that conducts rigorous individual interviews with a small number of participants to explore their perceptions of a particular idea (Boyce & Neale, 2006).

➤ *Research Instrument:*

In this phenomenological study, the research questions made by the researcher were made according to the data needed. The instruments used in this qualitative type of study are interview questions and tape recorder for credibility purposes and end at focus group discussion of the respondents in every selected school. According to Bernard (1988), semi-structured interview is best used when you cannot get more than one chance to interview someone and when you will be sending several interviewers out into the field to collect data. These are often lead by observation, informal and unstructured interviewing in order to allow the researchers to develop a keen understanding of the topic of interest necessary for developing relevant and meaningful semi-structured questions. The respondents of the study were given main guide questions ahead of time, which was tackled

and followed by some open-ended questions that diverged some questions from the interview guide depending on their answers. The questions are composed and asked in English and Filipino language, and they can utilize the language they were comfortable with for them to be able to convey what they want to express without uncertainty. Another tool that was used by the researcher in gathering data using the survey questionnaire.

III. RESULTS

This part contains detailed presentation and discussion of data analysis and the results of this study. The findings are presented under the following major headings: The profile of the respondents in terms of: a. Age; b. Family income; c. Occupation of the Parents; and d. Reasons for working while studying. The academic performance of the respondents. The challenging experiences encountered by the respondents along: a. Time management b. Academic Performance. Recommend a motivational program on action plan for the Senior High School working students.

A. *The Profile of the Respondents Age:*

The profile of the respondents in terms of: Age; the 11 respondents from Ponso National High School the age of the respondents ranges from 16-20 years old and from the 9 respondents in Itaran National High School the age of the respondents ranges from 16-17 years old and the 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School the age ranges from 16-20 years old.

B. *Family Income:*

In terms of the Family income, the family income of the 11 respondents from Ponso National High School ranges from Php. 1,000 below, and from the 9 respondents in Itaran National High School the family income ranges from Php. 1,000 below, lastly, the 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School the family income ranges also from Php. 1,000 below.

C. *Occupation of the Parents:*

In terms of the Occupation of the Parents; the 11 respondents from Ponso National High School most of the Occupation of the Father of the respondents was Farmer, Construction Worker and Tricycle Driver, for the occupation of the mother of the respondent, most of the occupation was housewife and from the 9 respondents in Itaran National High School, most of the Occupation of the Father of the respondents was Vegetable Vendor, Construction Worker and Tricycle Driver and for the occupation of the mother of the respondent, most of the occupation was Housewife and Babysitter. The 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School most of the Occupation of the Father of the respondents was Farmer, Construction Worker, Tricycle Driver and some of the respondents' father was deceased, for the occupation of the mother of the respondent, most of the occupation was Housewife and Sari-sari Store Owner.

D. Reason for Working While Studying:

Making the decision to work alongside the education is something that many students think about or perhaps battle with. Some of the students' reason for working while studying is to make experience and also to help their parents. In this study, the working student respondents were asked some personal questions. In terms of the reason for working while studying the guide question is:

Reason for working while studying
Bakit mas pinili mo ang magtrabaho habang nag-aaral?

➤ *The 11 respondents from Ponso National High School Answered:*

- *Participant 1:*
To help my parents especially since their income is not enough for daily expenses)
- *Participant 2:*
To help my family and to provide money for my studies.
- *Participant 3:*
I prefer to work while studying because while studying it helps my parents as well as my younger siblings.
- *Participant 4:*
To help the family.
- *Participant 5:*
So that my parents don't have to worry about my daily life at school.
- *Participant 6:*
So I chose to work while studying because of our state of life. My father does not earn enough from the farm that we live on. So I thought of working while studying to help support the household expenses and also help my parents.
- *Participant 7:*
To no longer depend on parents. I preferred to work while studying to help my family.
- *Participant 8:*
I chose to work while studying because of the lack of support on a daily basis and my studies that my parents could not support so it is necessary to study and work at the same time.
- *Participant 9:*
To help my parents in terms of finances and provide additional support to our expenses.
- *Participant 10:*
To provide my own expenses.
- *Participant 11:*
To also help with the family's expenses and needs and provide for oneself.

➤ *The 9 respondents from Itaran National High School:*

- *Participant 1:*
The particular reason for the circumstances is that I wanted to help my parents in their financial expenses by providing my own needs as a student.
 - *Participant 2:*
I chose to work while studying to help with the household expenses and so that my parents wouldn't have to suffer anymore and also to pay for the school expenses.)
 - *Participant 3:*
To help my family's finances.
 - *Participant 4:*
Because my parents' income is insufficient that's why I thought of working while studying so that I can also help in our daily life.
 - *Participant 5:*
The reason why I'm a working student because to provide my needs in school and also to help my family expenses.
 - *Participant 6:*
Because my father didn't earn enough to educate my siblings.
 - *Participant 7:*
Because we don't have much of money to provide my needs and to help also my parents instead of giving to my younger siblings.
 - *Participant 8:*
For extra income to help with the family's daily life.
 - *Participant 9:*
I preferred to work while studying because nowadays the situation is difficult, I want to help not only myself but also my family. I also want to experience being independent, not depending on parents or family.
- *The 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School:*
- *Participant 1:*
For me to support my studies and also to help my family.
 - *Participant 2:*
To buy everything I need and not ask my parents.)
 - *Participant 3:*
To help my parents in any way and so that I don't have to ask for money for my school needs.)

- *Participant 4:*
To help my family and my studies so that I won't have to ask for support for my studies and also so that I can give something to my parents.
 - *Participant 5:*
Because as a student I have needs and projects and need to finance the expenses so I chose to work while studying.
 - *Participant 6:*
To help the family and to have money for school.
 - *Participant 7:*
Because we are in a big family the everyday needs aren't enough to support us.
 - *Participant 8:*
Because it will help me to buy my needs and it will help my family.
 - *Participant 9:*
Because it will help me for my expenses in school and my mother financially.
 - *Participant 10:*
To help the family and lessen the expenses that are being asked to my parents.
 - *Participant 11:*
Because there are days when we are short of daily needs. at home and in school.)
 - *Participant 12:*
To help with study expenses. To help parents and to gain work experience.
 - *Participant 13:*
To help myself and my family.
 - *Participant 14:*
To help my parents financially and also to provide my needs especially to my school expenses.
 - *Participant 15:*
To be able to help my family to earn more money and also to experience some hardship in life to prepare myself in the near future.
 - *Participant 16:*
So that I can help my parents and also to support myself from studying, not just depending in my parents.
- ❖ *The Academic Performance of the Respondents:*
- *The 11 respondents from Ponso National High School:*
- *Participant 1:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 87
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 87
 - *Participant 2:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 90
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
 - *Participant 3:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 90
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
 - *Participant 4:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 90
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 88
 - *Participant 5:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 88
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 91
 - *Participant 6:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 86
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
 - *Participant 7:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 88
 - *Participant 8:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 88
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 86
 - *Participant 9:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 84
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 85
 - *Participant 10:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 89
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
 - *Participant 11:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 94
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
- *The 9 Respondents from Itaran National High School:*
- *Participant 1:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 84
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 81
 - *Participant 2:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 89

- *Participant 3:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 91
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 92
- *Participant 4:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 89
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
- *Participant 5:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 90
- *Participant 6:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 85
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
- *Participant 7:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 84
- *Participant 8:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 83
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
- *Participant 9:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 86
- *The 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School:*
- *Participant 1:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 90
- *Participant 2:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 91
- *Participant 3:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 89
- *Participant 4:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 92
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
- *Participant 5:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 91
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
- *Participant 6:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 95
- *Participant 7:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 91
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 92
- *Participant 8:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 90
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 89
- *Participant 9:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 85
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 88
- *Participant 10:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 91
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 88
- *Participant 11:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 85
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 87
- *Participant 12:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 90
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
- *Participant 13:*
Grade 11
Average for first semester for Grade 11: 94
- *Participant 14:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 83
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 90
- *Participant 15:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 88
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 87
- *Participant 16:*
Grade 12
General Weighted Average for Grade 11: 96
Average for first semester for Grade 12: 96
- ❖ *The Challenging Experiences Encountered by the Respondents Along:*
- E. *Time Management:*
In terms of the time management, the guide question is:
What challenges have you faced when working while studying in terms of Time Management and how do you overcome the problems?

➤ *The 11 respondents from Ponso National High School:*

- *Participant 1:*
Tired, sleepy but just enduring it for the sake of my family, I just laugh at the problem.
- *Participant 2:*
For me, I'm always sleep deprived. I always have to do double-time. In order to manage my time, I need to finish the work lined up immediately, especially when studying.
- *Participant 3:*
For me, what I experience as a working student is tiredness, because after working I still have to study even though I'm tired. As for time-management, it needs to be balanced so that I don't get overwhelmed with work, especially with our school activities.
- *Participant 4:*
I can't manage my time and sometimes lack of sleep because I have to finish schoolwork. But I can overcome this because my family and friends help me especially in doing homework and activities.
- *Participant 5:*
The challenges I'm facing is that sometimes I can't go to school but I make it works. Sometimes I ask my classmates what the activities or projects are so that I won't be late in the deadline.
- *Participant 6:*
The challenge that I face as a working student is the pursuit of what our teacher teaches. What I do to manage my time is to borrow notebooks from my classmates.
- *Participant 7:*
The challenge I face is sleepiness and tiredness, but I overcome it by resting, especially on weekends with my friends and family.
- *Participant 8:*
The challenge I face in balancing work and study time is that I don't focus well on my studies and rarely attend school so my grades are low. I focus more on my work so I find it difficult to keep up with my studies.
- *Participant 9:*
Lack of time is one of my problems. I make sure to make schedules for my tasks both in school and in work to balance my time well.
- *Participant 10:*
Lack of time for school and homework. But I make sure that I still balance my studies and work.
- *Participant 11:*
It's very difficult because of the schedule and time limit, sometimes I don't get much sleep. Just considering it in prayer.

➤ *The 9 respondents from Itaran National High School:*

- *Participant 1:*
Some challenges that I faced when working while studying I sometimes missed some of my lessons. It is because my night-shift work. However, I can still handle it smoothly.
 - *Participant 2:*
The challenge that I face in balancing my time is that I balance reviewing for the examination while at work and submitting what is needed for school. I overcome them through hard work and determination.
 - *Participant 3:*
I can't do the activities anymore. I always do this when it's late at night and there's no work.
 - *Participant 4:*
Sometimes I lose time to sleep because I go to school early in the morning because I work at night for our family.
 - *Participant 5:*
The challenges that I face as a working student, especially when it comes to time-management, sometimes I can no longer focus on my studies but I have overcome it because I now think carefully about how I manage my time.
 - *Participant 6:*
I'm having a hard time because I'm not getting enough sleep and other school work that I can't do sometimes. I overcome this problem because I have my brothers and sisters who always help me.
 - *Participant 7:*
The challenge I faced as a working student is that sometimes I have a lot of school activities to do but I can still manage my time because I do them one by one and still I can catch up with the deadline.
 - *Participant 8:*
The problem I face is time-management. Because there are times that our teachers want us to submit an activity at the same time. But I'm managing it because I'm talking to my teachers to give me enough time to submit because I'm a self-support student.
 - *Participant 9:*
The challenge I experience with time-managing as a working student is that I am sometimes late to submit a project. But I was able to overcome it because I asked my teachers for another chance to submit.
- *The 16 respondents from Polangui General Comprehensive High School:*
- *Participant 1:*
I experienced not being accepted at work but I proved that I can be a student and a worker at the same time because it is for my family.

- *Participant 2:*

I used to study in the morning and work in the evening. Even if it's hard, I can handle it just time-management.)

- *Participant 3:*

Time-management is all that is needed and as a working student it is really a challenge but I can do it for my family and for my dreams.)

- *Participant 4:*

I always face the lack of time because as a student it is very difficult to work and study at the same time so I am always short on time but I will not give up for my dream even if it is difficult I can handle it for my family.

- *Participant 5:*

My problem as a working student is that sometimes I eat late and don't sleep enough. I overcame these problems because of the help of my Mother who always reminded me and always prepared food for me.

- *Participant 6:*

The challenges I experience as a working student are often being late to school. So it's unfortunate that I'm late or I didn't catch up with other subjects but I am still giving time to my studies.

- *Participant 7:*

The challenges I face while studying and working are that I miss-out some lessons and activities since I am lacking time and focus.

- *Participant 8:*

My problem as a working student is that I feel tired from work but I still have to study or review the lessons. As for time-management, it's not difficult because I can still do it together at the same time.

- *Participant 9:*

The challenges I face is balancing time between studying and working. Since I am a working student, I have to find good timing for everything I do.

- *Participant 10:*

I'm sleep deprived and it's hard to focus in class because of staying awake. I overcome the problem by believing in myself that I can overcome it.

- *Participant 11:*

The challenging part as a working student is the deadline for the projects because I don't have enough time and instead of getting failing grades, I would rather talk to my teachers so that I can be given another chance to be able to submit my projects.

- *Participant 12:*

What I face in balancing time while working and studying is the time between working and studying. What I do is, I study in the morning and work in the evening.

- *Participant 13:*

I experienced entering the classroom tired but I showed that I can do it because it is for my future and for the family.

- *Participant 14:*

The most challenging part of being a working student is that I am tired but have to take the Examination. It's hard when there's an exam especially and I can't review, so in order to balance my work, when we have an exam I don't go to work to review. I'm happy with what I'm doing especially and I am now a Grade 12 student.

- *Participant 15:*

There are a lot of challenges and sometimes time-management is really hard to maintain especially when there's a lot of school works. But thanks to my family and friends they help me and they are keep on supporting me.

- *Participant 16:*

It is very difficult to be a student but I have to work hard to graduate because I have a dream that I want to achieve.

F. Academic Performance:

In terms of Academic Performance, the guide question is:

What challenges have you faced when working while studying in terms of Academic Performance?

➤ *The 11 respondents from Ponso National High School:*

Late for activities because a working student's time is limited)

- *Participant 2:*

For me I find it hard the fact that I face a lot of difficulties when I sometimes missed some lessons, but I make sure that I will do my best even though I am left behind. Thus, I may say that I do my best always.

- *Participant 3:*

For me, my biggest problem as a working student, especially in academic performance, is that I can no longer keep up with class. So for me that is the hardest thing I've ever experienced.

- *Participant 4:*

One of my problems as a working student was that my grades really dropped.

- *Participant 5:*

The challenge I'm facing is that I haven't been able to follow up on our lesson because I've been busy with my work. I can still handle it because I am asking my teacher about the lesson.

- *Participant 6:*

In this situation, no matter how hard it is to combine studying and working, I don't neglect my studies. In the difficult situation, I get good grades because I persevere in studying and working.

- *Participant 7:*

Late activities or output, low grades are the examples of my problems that I face as a working student. But I'm happy because I'm still studying. My dream is to go to college and graduate.

- *Participant 8:*

The challenges I face academically are not being able to go to class sometimes, late, low grades sometimes it seems like I want to stop studying.

- *Participant 9:*

I often feel drained and tired when I am at school because of too many backlogs. Being tired during class discussion affects my activeness in class and it also affects performance academically.

- *Participant 10:*

Sleeping in school and my mind is not functioning well.

- *Participant 11:*

Time schedule and time management especially when there is an emergency.

➤ *The 9 respondents from Itaran National High School:*

- *Participant 1:*

There are times that I almost failed. Because I did not meet the deadline of the submission of the activities but some of my teachers are very considerate that's why they accept my activities even if it is already late.

- *Participant 2:*

The challenge I faced academically while I was studying and working, when the exam was near and I needed to review but I still had to work because my brother got sick then and I needed to earn money. In this situation, I really can't say that this will improve my academic performance.

- *Participant 3:*

Time management, because of it I am missing the activities and most of the time I am having difficulties to understand the lesson.

- *Participant 4:*

I am having a hard time catching up with our teacher's discussions even though my situation is like this I still submit my output.

- *Participant 5:*

The challenges that I face while I am studying and working, in terms of, academic performance I am getting a low grade sometimes.

- *Participant 6*

I have a hard time adapting lessons and catching up on tasks.

- *Participant 7:*

Sometimes I do not understand the lesson due to backlogs but I can catch up the lesson whenever my

classmates are letting me to borrow their notebooks. With this, I can pursuit in the lesson discussion.

- *Participant 8:*

I'm late in submitting the outputs.

- *Participant 9:*

It's hard to balance studying and working, so sometimes in graded recitation I really can't answer.

➤ *The 16 Respondents in Poalngui General Comprehensive High School:*

- *Participant 1:*

I only had a hard time when it was time for the exam.

- *Participant 2:*

In terms of time management, especially when there is a group activity that is to be performed and practice. If you do not cooperate, you will not be given a grade and it affects my academic performance.

- *Participant 3:*

Sometimes I am not given consideration when I am late and because of that I am getting low grade.

- *Participant 4:*

Sometimes I run out of time to submit projects and sometimes I don't have time to participate in the activities. I would love to participate but it is inevitable that there are emergencies that come up and work has to be chosen. Sometimes it crossed my mind to just stop studying.

- *Participant 5:*

The challenges I face are always being late from work and being sleepy in the classroom due to lack of sleep.

- *Participant 6:*

It's hard to work while studying because you don't have time for everything, so sometimes you can't balance studying and working.

- *Participant 7:*

Due to my work it affects my performance level where I sometimes can't answer the questions on our class recitation and therefore it affects my grades.

- *Participant 8:*

Maybe for me everything is tiring because there is nothing easy, there are so many struggles at work, at school, with money I don't know what to do anymore so it affects my academic performance as a student.

- *Participant 9:*

The lack of sleep and having a breakdown in the middle of doing things.

- *Participant 10:*

Unable to focus properly due to lack of life.

- *Participant 11:*

For me, it was almost difficult for me to do the activities at school because I was always focused on work.

- *Participant 12:*

The challenge I'm facing academically while working and studying, sometimes when I am at work I'm thinking about the activities I'll do at school. My mind is crowded but needs to be widened.

- *Participant 13:*

I experienced going to school without sleep but I have to persevere for my future and for my family.

- *Participant 14:*

Sometimes I couldn't answer our quiz because I arrived late and couldn't submit my output on time. Because it is inevitable that academic performance is low.

- *Participant 15:*

In my own experience it's ok to be late than to be absent, even if I'm late, I will attend in the class, maybe this is the reason why I don't fail in my subjects.

- *Participant 16:*

There is just a little conflict in my academic performance and that is being late in submitting the outputs this is also the reason why I am having a low grade but I am glad that I do not have any failing grades.

IV. DISCUSSION

The respondents with respect to their distinctive characteristics and live experiences somehow showed similarities in some aspects. In this study, the researcher realized what are the roles of a working student and how important the education for the working student respondents. Working students are those who support themselves financially so they can pursue their education, either with or without their parents' help. They are devoted individuals who live and serve others in return for money to support their education.

Education is a guide to everyone. People's minds are greatly expanded through education, which also aids in eradicating social divisions. It equips us with the skills necessary to excel in school and comprehend all facets of life. It gives one the capacity to comprehend all of one's national obligations, social rights, and human rights. A person's future is built by their education, which also qualifies them for better opportunities in life and job options. It results in a man being groomed and qualifies him for job opportunities for a stable future and career. With education, there are many opportunities to be financially independent. The external world requires a degree as well as practical experience. Without education, it is impossible to find a great career or to be in a situation where one may work for oneself and make a living.

Meanwhile, with regards to the challenging experiences of the respondents, based on their narratives, they told me

that they have become more independent and resilient. They also shared the same sentiments with regards to the challenges they are experiencing. The study also showed that the dreams and family are important. In this sense, after deep reflection and analysis of the nature of their experience, this study has allowed me to symbolize the phenomenon as bamboo in a storm. It is not easy to be a working student because the enemy is time and fatigue. It is forbidden to give up because this is a sign of giving up on the dream. A bamboo may be an image for life span since of its strength, quality, adaptability and versatility. It survives the harshest conditions, and appears to persevere through all the brutalities Mother Nature gives- still standing tall and remaining green year-round. Its adaptability and flexibility are lessons bestowed to us.

The bamboo perseveres the harshest downpours and storm season and greatly hot summer and is some of the time the as it were "thing" cleared out standing within the field after the storm. Comparative to what my respondents do to proceed living and serving the individuals. They might have endured challenges at to begin with such as adjusting to the modern typical and stood up with respect and pride. Cristobal (2021)

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the responses and in depth synthesis, the following conclusions are made: Working students can gain a lot of various benefits from working while studying. However, most students feel that having these jobs can distract them from their studies. The academic performance of the respondents depends on how the working students handle their time-management. The challenging experiences encountered by the respondents along time-management, are: lack time for working on activity that they are always late in submitting their prepared activity. In terms of their, academic performance, they are having passing grades but low.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Sumalinog, G. G. (2018). Working Local, Going Global: Challenges and Opportunities of Working Students Teaching English as a Second Language.
- [2]. Remenick, L., & Bergman, M. (2021). Support for working students: Considerations for higher education institutions. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 69(1), 34-45. Lee, J. C., & Staff, J. (2007). When work matters: The varying impact of work intensity on high school dropout. *Sociology of Education*, 80(2), 158-178.
- [3]. Tsurugano, S., Nishikitani, M., Inoue, M., & Yano, E. (2021). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on working students: Results from the Labour Force Survey and the student lifestyle survey. *Journal of Occupational Health*, 63(1), e12209.
- [4]. Peteros, E. D. (2021). Understanding the Effects of Time Management and Self-Efficacy on math Performance among High School Students Working Part-Time in Cebu, Philippines. *Information Technology in Industry*, 9(2), 1077-1085.

- [5]. EBARDO, R., & WIBOWO, S. (2021). I Work to Learn: The Lived Experiences of Working Students in Online Learning during COVID-19. In *The 29th International Conference on Computers in Education 2021* (pp. 1-4).
- [6]. Zhang, G., Shao, C. Y., & Johnston, C. R. (2019). Working Students and Their Academic Performance—A Decision Tree Analysis. *Journal of Higher Education Theory & Practice*, 19(7).
- [7]. Mutya, R. C., Geverola, I. J. R., Cano Jr, A. C., & Friolo, R. V. (2022). Coping with uncertainties: Unveiling the lived experiences of working students in the new normal. *HO CHI MINH CITY OPEN UNIVERSITY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE-SOCIAL SCIENCES*, 12(1), 112-129.
- [8]. Neyt, B., Omev, E., Verhaest, D., & Baert, S. (2019). Does student work really affect educational outcomes? A review of the literature. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 33(3), 896-921.
- [9]. Saveanu, S. M., & ȘTEFĂNESCU, F. (2019). Working or Learning? Working Students in the Romanian-Hungarian Cross-Border Area. *Romanian Journal for Multidimensional Education/Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 11(4).
- [10]. Tumin, T., Faizuddin, A., Mansir, F., Purnomo, H., & Aisyah, N. (2020). Working Students in Higher Education: Challenges and Solutions. *Al-Hayat: Journal of Islamic Education*, 4(1), 79-89.
- [11]. Nurwulan, N. R., & Selamaj, G. (2020). Working university students in riau archipelago: dual role and depression. *Jurnal Educativ: Journal of Educational Studies*, 5(2), 123-135.
- [12]. Hermawan, P. P., & Astuti, N. W. (2021, August). An Overview of Learning Motivation Among Working Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic. In *International Conference on Economics, Business, Social, and Humanities (ICEBSH 2021)* (pp. 1322-1327). Atlantis Press.
- [13]. Koropets, O., Fedorova, A., & Kacane, I. (2019). THE MODEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT FOR WORKING STUDENTS WITH THE EMOTIONAL BURNOUT SYNDROME. In *12th Annual International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation (ICERI)* (pp. 10377-10383). International Academy of Technology, Education and Development.
- [14]. Mutya, R. C., Geverola, I. J. R., Cano Jr, A. C., & Friolo, R. V. (2022). Coping with uncertainties: Unveiling the lived experiences of working students in the new normal. *HO CHI MINH CITY OPEN UNIVERSITY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE-SOCIAL SCIENCES*, 12(1), 112-129.
- [15]. Savoca, M. (2016). Campus employment as a high impact practice: Relationship to academic success and persistence of first-generation college students (Doctoral dissertation, Colorado State University).
- [16]. Hingada, R. M., Yayong, M. T. M., Florita, J., & Platilla, J. (2019). Level of Interest of Senior High School Working Students of Etmnhs-Ishs in Pursuing College Courses Academic Year 2018-2019. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2F).
- [17]. Solmiano, E. M., Buenaobra, J. R., Santiago, M. P., Rivera, Y., Del Rosario, A., Hung, P., & Tus, J. Kayod Kalabaw: The Phenomenological Study of the Experiences and Challenges Faced By Working Students Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic.
- [18]. Peprah, W. K., Mattu, A. G., & Antwi-Yamoah, P. B. (2019, December). Compensation and social support on continuance commitment of working students in Adventist University of the Philippines. In *Abstract Proceedings International Scholars Conference (Vol. 7, No. 1, pp. 1044-1053)*.
- [19]. Garado, B. A., Inductivo, H. M., Rodriguez, G. F., Villahermosa, J. C., & Villegas, G. P. (2019). An Assessment on the Difficulties encountered by the HUMSS SHS Working Students of Bestlink College of the Philippines. *Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1).
- [20]. Astudillo, M. L., Martos, R., Reese, T. M., Umpad, K. J., & Fuente, A. D. (2019). The Effects of Time Management among Working Students of Selected Grade 12 General Academic Strand of Senior High School in Bestlink College of the Philippines. *Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1).
- [21]. Porbible, M., De Guzman, J. M., Tormes, J., Reandino, C. R., Rodriguez, A. M., & Perfecto, M. G. A. (2019). Factors Affecting the Academic Performance of Grade 12 ABM Working Students in Bestlink College of the Philippines SY 2018-2019. *Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1).
- [22]. Montaner, J., Garcia, D., Yunsay, C. J., Guillen, J., Pagunsan, J. M., & Amar, J. (2020). Effects of Workloads on Academic Performance of Working Students among Third Year Students of College of Education: A Guide. *Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1).
- [23]. Coral, A. F., Atillo, E. D., Baldoviso, J. J., Binigay Jr, R., Bugtong, J., & Bernales Jr, G. (2020). Challenges Encountered By Working Students that Affect their Academic Performance. *Ascendens Asia Singapore–Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1).
- [24]. Cabrera, A. K. C., Lumibao, P. A. B., Manabat, C. M. V., & Masangkay, P. B. (2017). WORKING SCHOLAR™: A Qualitative Research on the Time Management of College Students who are Working Scholars in St. Mary's College, Quezon City. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 1(1).
- [25]. <https://www.urgentessayhelp.co.uk/blog/challenges-working-students-encounter-in-daily-life/>